

Interaction of catechol with Fe^{III} tripodal ligand complex in aqueous surfactant medium : A kinetic approach

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Abstract : The oxygenation reaction of catechol (cat²⁻) with ferric complex [Fe(NTA)] (NTA = nitrilotriacetate) has been studied in aqueous surfactant medium. The oxygenation reaction is observed to follow pseudo-first order pathway in cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactant medium. These rate constant values are validated and enzyme kinetics of the oxygenation reaction has also been thoroughly examined. The results of the kinetics experiment may be considered as dioxygenase enzyme mimics.

Keywords : Catechol, tripodal ligand, surfactant, oxygenation reaction, enzyme kinetics.

Introduction

Soil bacteria helps in the biodegradation by the oxidative cleavage of aromatic vicinal diols specially catechol. Catechol dioxygenases are the class of non-heme iron enzymes that catalyze this oxidative cleavage of catechol and its analogs. On the basis of regiospecificity, dioxygenases are classified into two ways, (a) intradiol dioxygenases, which utilize non-heme Fe^{III} centre by surface activation mechanism and (b) extradiol dioxygenase generally using non-heme Fe^{II} centre via oxygenation activation mechanism¹⁻⁷.

Fig. 1. Enzyme catalyzed reactions of intradiol dioxygenases.

Many attempts to model the catechol dioxygenases have been reported. In these cases the ligand which are used to prepare complexes with metal centre always resemble the active site of intradiol dioxygenase¹⁻³. Que and co-workers have proposed a surface activation mechanism for the cleaving reaction. They proposed a novel substrate for oxygenation reaction where the substrate deprotonated twice to coordinate with the Fe^{III} ion. The electron transfer from iron centre to ligand give semiquinone character to the

bound substrate. The attack of dioxygen on the activated substrate yields a peroxy radical which generate alkylperoxyiron(III) species. The peroxy adduct decomposes by a Criegee-type rearrangement to muconic anhydride¹⁻⁴.

In this study we have reported the kinetics of the oxygenation reaction of catechol by Fe^{III} tripodal ligand complex [Fe(NTA)] in aqueous micellar medium. Tripodal ligand nitrilotriacetic acid (i.e. NTA) is utilized in this effort as it resemble the active site environment of catechol-1,2-dioxygenase. The main objective of this work is to support the projection of [Fe(NTA)] as a model of catechol dioxygenase enzyme. Phenolic byproducts are common waste of paper and oil industries. These wastes are mostly carcinogenic. So any alternative chemical way of conversion of such toxic products into less toxic aliphatic compounds are always of interest⁴. To mimic the reaction medium with biomembrane system, aqueous surfactant medium is used for the analysis of this attempt. CTAB, SDS and Triton X-100 are used as cationic, anionic and neutral surfactant medium respectively.

Results and discussion

In this work we examined the interaction of catechol with Fe^{III} tripodal ligand complex [Fe^{III}(NTA)(OH)₂]²⁻

at high pH level (i.e. $\text{pH} > \text{pK}_a$). On addition of 1 equivalent of catechol (1 mM) to an aqueous surfactant solution of ferric complex $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{NTA})(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ (1 mM) at high pH value ($\text{pH} 10.5\text{--}11.0$), new bands in the range 570–580 nm and 370–385 nm are observed. Comparing these spectral positions with the spectra of related phenolate complexes of iron^{4,6} the band around 570–580 nm (ϵ , $200\text{--}300 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is assigned to phenolate $p_\pi \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(d\pi^*)$ LMCT transition and band around 370–390 nm (ϵ , $500\text{--}600 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is assigned to ligand based band. The colour of the solution changed from light violet to red. The band at 580 nm in the visible region is an indication of binding of cat^{2-} to iron in $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{NTA})(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ complex^{8–10}.

The CT transition is quite sensitive to the nature of the environment around Fe and to the nature of the solvent. The electronic band position undergoes change during gradual addition of cat^{2-} to $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{NTA})(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ in aqueous surfactant micelle (CTAB) at $\text{pH} \approx 10.5\text{--}11.0$. The intensity of band at 580 nm gradually grows and simultaneously the intensity of the high energy band at 390 nm decreases. These spectral changes form isosbestic points at 348 nm and 450 nm indicating bidentate binding mode of cat^{2-} with Schiff base complex.

The investigation of the oxygenation reaction of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{NTA})(\text{cat})]^{2-}$ adduct, which is produced *in situ* (with the help of base), has been done in aqueous surfactant medium. The reaction is analyzed by monitoring the slow change of the absorbance of the phenolate(π) \rightarrow iron(III)($d\pi^*$) LMCT band (λ_{max} 580 nm). Gradual decrease of absorbance, at band position 580 nm (λ_{max}), with time indicates the decomposition of the substrate. The reactivity of the oxygenation reaction in aqueous surfactant medium can be exemplified by comparing the change of absorbance (λ_{max} 580 nm) both in presence or absence of O_2 ^{11–13}.

The oxygenation reaction is carried out in all the three micellar media using following procedure : $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{NTA})]$ is encapsulated in aqueous cationic surfactant micelle (CTAB). The pH of the solution is increased to 10.5 and equivalent molar amount of substrate (i.e. cat^{2-}) is made to react with complex. The interaction

of substrate with Fe^{III} complex is evident from the change of colour of solution to violet. The solution of substrate- Fe^{3+} complex adduct is exposed to O_2 (air) at room temperature. The oxygenation kinetics is measured by monitoring the slow disappearance of the lower energy charge transfer band at λ_{max} 580 nm as shown in the Fig. 2. The process is considered as pseudo-first order kinetics in presence of large concentration of dioxygen^{6,12}. The elec-

Fig. 2. Progress of the reaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})(\text{cat})]^{2-}$ (generated *in situ*) encapsulated in CTAB micelle with air at 27 °C monitored by UV-Visible spectroscopy. The spectra are shown at 1 min intervals.

tronic spectrum of the reaction mixture after 36 h show the disappearance of the 580 nm band indicating the completion of the oxygenation reaction. The rate constant (k_{obs}) was calculated by fitting the decrease in intensity of the band into the following equation applicable for relatively slow reaction

$$A = A_\alpha + (A_0 - A_\alpha) \exp(-k_{\text{obs}} t)$$

where t is the time, A , A_0 and A_α are the absorbance at the time t , 0 and α respectively, and k_{obs} is the pseudo-first order rate constant (Fig. 3). The second order rate constant K_{O_2} is then calculated from the equation^{4–6,12,14–17}.

$$K_{\text{O}_2} = \frac{K_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{O}_2]}$$

The oxygenation reaction is also studied in anionic (SDS) and neutral aqueous micellar solution (Triton X-100) (Table 1). The rate of the oxygenation reaction indicates that rate of the reaction depends on the nature of the surfactants and Lewis acidity of the ferric complex. For

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log(A - A_{\infty})$ vs time observed at 580 nm of $[\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})(\text{cat})]^{2-}$ (generated *in situ*) with O_2 at 27 °C in CTAB micelle.

Table 1. Kinetic data for the oxidative cleavage of $[\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})(\text{cat})]^{2-}$ in different aqueous surfactant micelles at 27 °C temperature (analyzed after 36 h)

Solvent	k_{obs} (10^{-5} s^{-1})	K_{O_2} ($10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
CTAB	10.5 ± 0.2	8.7 ± 0.1
SDS	17.3 ± 0.1	15.6 ± 0.2
Triton X-100	6.6 ± 0.1	5.2 ± 0.2

$[\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})(\text{cat})]^{2-}$ adduct rate of the oxygenation reaction in surfactant micelles decreases in the order $\text{SDS} > \text{CTAB} > \text{Triton X-100}$.

The activity of the ferric complexes can be compared with catechol-1,2-dioxygenase and it is exemplified with *in situ* prepared complexes. The reactivity and position of the M→L CT band is influenced by the amount of base added to the reaction mixture of catechol and ferric complex. Addition of base assists deprotonation of the substrate. Highly favourable reaction condition is provided by the addition of approximately 1 to 2 equivalent bases and consequently UV-Visible bands are shifted to a minimum energy. However, very high concentration of base retards the reaction rate due to competitive coordination of base to ferric centre. Experiments are carried out for each complex at the highest possible reaction rate. For comparable kinetic results the exact amount of base was determined before reaction^{18–21}.

The addition of the reagents and solvents are always carried out in the order : micelle, $[\text{Fe}(\text{L})]^+$, catechol and base. The rate of product formation at 390 nm is linear over time up to 10 min when final concentration of $[\text{Fe}(\text{L})]^+$ and catechol are each 0.3 mM. The effect of changing the

relative concentration of the four reagents led to varied behaviour. Saturation kinetics is examined by plotting initial rates (V_0) vs concentration of catechol ($[\text{S}]$) (Fig. 4).

According to best known model of enzyme kinetics (Michaelis-Menten kinetics) K_m (Michaelis constant), V_{max} (maximum rate achieved by the system) and k_{cat} (turn over number) are calculated by applying Lineweaver-Burk or Eadie-Hofstee plots (Table 2). From the initial velocity measurements (V_0) the values of K_m and V_{max} can be obtained in several ways, like, substrate saturation curve (Fig. 4A), double reciprocal plot (Fig. 4B) and Eadie-Hofstee plot (Fig. 4C) are reported. K_m , V_{max} and k_{cat}/K_m values obtained from these different experimental plots are in well agreement with each other. These values strongly suggest that the complex of $[\text{Fe}(\text{L})]^+$, the “active site” of the model reaction, is formed before combining with the substrate. The constant k_{cat}/K_m indicate the efficiency of the concern enzyme. These values encourage the utility of the proposed enzyme^{1,14}.

Conclusion

The proposed ring cleavages of catechol supported by ferric tripodal ligand complex in aqueous surfactant medium have been characterized experimentally. The rates of the oxygenation reaction have been influenced by the nature of the medium as well as the Lewis acidity of the metal ion. In addition to that another important factor that could responsible of the rates of oxygenation reaction is that the product release is the rate determining phase of the catalytic reaction^{3–21}. Study of the enzyme kinetics of the oxygenation reaction also encourages the utility of proposed Schiff base complex as a model of catechol dioxygenase. It is remarkable that the N-based complex confers as enhanced reaction rate with efficient conversion of substrate to intradiol cleavage products.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Nitritotriacetate (NTA) was purchased from Merck chemicals. The synthetic procedure of ferric complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{NTA})]$ formation is obtained from a previous report².

We used cationic micelle CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide), anionic micelle SDS (sodium dodecylsulphate) and neutral micelles Triton X-100 in our experiments and all micelles were purchased from Sigma

Fig. 4. Kinetic behaviour of model reaction of [Fe(NTA)] with substrate catechol (cat^{2-}) in CTAB.

Table 2. Steady state kinetic parameters for [Fe(NTA)] with substrate cat^{2-} in different aqueous micellar medium

Medium	K_m (μM)	k_{cat} (s^{-1})	k_{cat}/K_m ($\text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
CTAB	80	44.1×10^{-1}	5.5×10^4
SDS	97	38.2×10^{-1}	3.9×10^4
Triton X-100	89	40.9×10^{-1}	4.5

Chemicals Co., USA and used without further purifications. Tetramethylammonium bromide (TMAB) were obtained from Spectrochem. Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. The

TMAB was used as counter ion in micelles. UV-Visible spectra were recorded in a Hitachi U-3210 model as well as in Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 UV/Vis spectrometer. The oxygenation kinetics experiments were performed in a 10 mm path length Thunberg quartz cuvette. pH dependent measurements were made by Adair Dupp. and Co. (India) model number DPH-77 pH meter. The pH electrode was SCE glass combined electrode which was standardized with known buffer solution. Throughout the work 2%, 4% and 3% (w/v) solution of SDS, CTAB and Tri-

ton X-100 are used. These concentrations are adjusted above the level of critical micellar concentration (cmc). It favours the complete micellization of the complex and also reduce the chance of any change in mid point redox potential value due to any minor fluctuation in the micelle concentration.

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